

PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS OF DEVELOPING LIFE SKILLS OF A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE AT ALL LEVELS OF THE POPULATION

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Abstract. *One of the main tasks of the society is to popularize knowledge about organizing a healthy lifestyle among the people. The article is devoted to the problem of health and the formation of a healthy lifestyle.*

Keywords: *lifestyle, solution, method, health, medicine.*

INTRODUCTION

Health has always been considered the highest value, which is an important basis for an active creative life, happiness, joy and well-being of a person. Health status is the most important indicator of the well-being of society and the state, reflecting not only the current situation, but also giving an accurate forecast for the future.

The main reasons for the deterioration of health are a low standard of living, an irresponsible attitude towards one's health, and low material support for health care institutions, sports and educational institutions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In the pursuit of intellectual development and high education, the fundamental basis for the full and harmonious development of the individual is lost - its physical and spiritual health. New teaching tools and technologies are being actively introduced into public schools. Researchers note that at all levels of education for young people there is no training in a healthy lifestyle, development of skills to adhere to it, and motivation for adequate behavior is reduced.

In the words of Adam Smith, the Scottish thinker, "Life and health are the chief concern of every man by nature. Concerns about our own health, about our own well-being, about everything that concerns our safety and our happiness, constitute the subject of the virtue called prudence. It does not allow us to risk our health, our well-being, our good name. In a word, prudence aimed at preserving health is considered a respectable quality" [1].

The French philosopher Claude Helvetius wrote in his writings about the positive influence of physical education on human health: "The task of this type of education is to make a person stronger, more robust, healthier, therefore, happier, more often benefiting their fatherland."

Thus, the great philosophers and thinkers argued that the person himself, mainly, should think, take care of his health, well-being and strive to maintain it. Human happiness depends on this.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Currently, it is customary to distinguish several components (types) of health:

Somatic health is the current state of the organs and systems of the human body, the basis of which is the biological program of individual development, mediated by basic needs. These needs are a mechanism for human development and ensure the individualization of this process.

Physical health is the level of growth and development of organs and systems of the body, which is based on morphophysiological and functional reserves that provide adaptive reactions [2].

Mental health is a state of the mental sphere, the basis of which is a state of general mental comfort that ensures an adequate behavioral response. This state is determined by both biological and social needs, as well as the possibilities of satisfying them. Today, physiologists and hygienists recognize the stress that students experience as the main risk factor for health problems in children and adolescents at school. At the same time, it is necessary to clearly realize that it is not stress itself that is harmful, but the student's inability to positively experience negative emotions. Prolonged stay in a state of stress can serve as an impetus for the development of various pathologies, especially if the student suffers from chronic diseases. Another property of negative affective states is that negative emotions can accumulate and an "affective explosion" is possible due to the repetition of a traumatic situation or the absence of external stimuli on which negative emotions can be discharged.

Moral health is a complex of characteristics of the motivational and need-information sphere of life, the basis of which is determined by the system of values, attitudes and motives of behavior of an individual in society. Moral health is mediated by human spirituality, as it is connected with the universal truths of goodness, love and beauty.

Signs of health are [3]:

- specific (immune) and nonspecific resistance to damaging factors;
- indicators of growth and development;
- functional state and reserve capabilities of the body;
- level of moral-volitional and value-motivational attitudes.

According to the conclusion of WHO experts, if we take the level of health as 100%, then the state of health depends only 10% on the activities of the health care system, 20% on hereditary factors, and 20% on the state of the environment. And the remaining 50% depends on the person himself, on the lifestyle he leads.

A healthy lifestyle is a system of individual manifestations of personality (moral, spiritual, physical) in the spheres of various activities (educational, everyday, social), reflecting the attitude towards oneself, the social environment, the surrounding nature from the standpoint of health values and contributing to the preservation of appropriate age of stability of the body, maximum activity of the individual in everyday life and professional activities.

According to modern concepts, the concept of a healthy lifestyle includes the following components:

- giving up harmful addictions (smoking, drinking alcoholic beverages and drugs);
- optimal motor mode;
- balanced diet;
- hardening;
- personal hygiene;
- positive emotions.

It follows that the process of preserving and strengthening health will be effective in the formation of a healthy lifestyle based on value-motivational attitudes towards health.

Unfortunately, health is far from being in the foreground, but in essence it should be in the first place, that is, it should become the primary need.

Creating a healthy lifestyle is a complex problem. We cannot talk only about ways and methods of promoting health and preventing diseases. It is necessary to increase the role of personal qualities in the conscious and volitional acceptance of the principles of a healthy lifestyle, and concern for health and its strengthening should become value motives of behavior.

The issue related to health is one of the first places in everyone's life, and for almost everyone this problem is an unresolved issue. Very often we believe that health, well-being, and happiness will be provided to us by others - parents, the state, a doctor, a teacher, a psychic. But a person can and should take care of himself. Our health is in our hands. Everyone should understand this simple truth.

Having understood this, we must try to return to that harmony with all natural forces that man loses with the development of civilization. And, in the end, a civilized lifestyle should become synonymous with a healthy lifestyle. It is necessary to eradicate ignorance in the field of the health of our own body. It is important to arm yourself with knowledge and skills and listen to yourself [4].

Health is a priceless gift that nature gives. Can life be interesting and happy without him? But how often do we waste this gift, forgetting that it is easy to lose health, but very difficult to restore it.

CONCLUSION

How many people, having lost their health and acquired a "set" of all kinds of diseases, pounce on fashionable medicines and expect instant healing. But relief does not come. They continue to swallow powders, tablets, mixtures and do not want to think about what is the cause of the disease, why they have lost vigor, dexterity, and strength. The answer to these questions is often very simple. This is all due to the wrong lifestyle that they led before and continue to lead to this day.

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